

PRINCIPLES OF PRAGMATIC ANALYSIS OF DIRECTIVE SPEECH ACTS IN DIACHRONY

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Abstract: The relevance of the article is a system-activity and functional approach to the analysis of speech communication. The theoretical basis of the article is the theory of self-organizing systems, the theory of speech activity and the theory of speech acts in their refraction in historical pragma linguistics. The pragmatic evolution of the English language, considered as a systemic phenomenon, is interpreted as a consequence of the development of society, culture and the language system as a whole in their interaction and interrelation.

Key words: pragmatic, directive speech acts, communicative-functional paradigm of modern linguistics, principle, concept, historical, methodological, diachronic, grammar, research, complex sentence.

Historical pragma linguistics is one of the areas of the communicative-functional paradigm of modern linguistics, which explores the pragmatic characteristics of speech communication in their historical development. "Based on the activity approach and based on the understanding of communication as a system, historical pragmatics studies the constant and variable elements of speech acts and discourse, considers dynamic processes in verbal communication as a result of the self-development of language and changes in communicative needs determined by the dynamics of culture and society" [11]. Using the concept of paradigm as "the dominant view of language in any given era, associated with a certain philosophical movement and a certain direction in art" [13], as the dominant research approach to language, cognitive perspective, methodological orientation, broad scientific movement, the essence of historical pragma linguistics, following I.S. Shevchenko [12], is understood as one of the approaches within the communicative-functional paradigm among synchronic pragma linguistics, socio- and psycholinguistics, which determines the presence of a partial subject-methodological commonality of these areas of research.

The chosen course of diachronic research of directive speech acts - from function to linguistic form - has led to interest in the study of phenomena in the sphere of pragma linguistics (the essence and varieties of directive speech acts and associated illocutionary markers, performative verbs, communicative principles, etc.) to identify invariant and variable features of their functioning in various historical periods, which implies the widespread use of the basic concepts of pragma linguistics, developed within the framework of its synchronic direction.

Synchronic pragmatics serves as the most important source of historical pragma linguistics. There are several interpretations of pragma linguistics in science. This is the semiotic line of C. Morris and C. Pierce [14], subsequently developed in the three-component model of speech activity by Yu.S. Stepanov [13], who identified pragmatics as a section of the general theory of signs among syntax and semantics. In these models, semantics indicates the

relationship of a sign to objects in the surrounding world, syntactics indicates the relationship of signs among themselves.

Stimulated by the works of J. Austin, P. Grice, J. Searle [1,6], the intensive development of pragmatics in recent decades, the use of data from cognitive linguistics, psycho- and sociolinguistics for the analysis of the production, perception and storage of linguistic information, prepared a new understanding of pragma linguistics as a synthesized discipline. It is characterized by the interpretative orientation of research into verbal communication, which determines the connection of pragmatics with the theory of context: it is the context that provides the possibility of “changing the pragmatic meaning integrated with the semantics of the linguistic unit” [3]. Synthesized pragma linguistics involves going beyond semiotics and turning it into a section of the general theory of communication.

In European linguistics in recent years, two approaches to pragmatics have been distinguished: integrated, corresponding to its classical semiotic interpretation, and radical, considering linguistics and pragmatics as different but interacting cognitive areas [5]. The mutual complementarity of these approaches to pragma linguistics, their synthesis, allows us to present a holistic pragmatic theory based on knowledge of language performance and communicative competence.

In accordance with the goals and objectives of this study, pragma linguistics is interpreted as a synthesized discipline that combines interrelated areas of research on speech acts (SAT) and discourse (conversation analysis) [10, 14]. According to T. van Dijk's definition, “the ultimate goal of the pragmatic theory of language is to establish a connection between utterances (and, therefore, grammar), on the one hand, and various types of interaction (and, therefore, social sciences), on the other” [3]. Detailing the essence of paralinguistics suggests that this is “the communicative aspect of language, focused on the study of the final result - the effect of linguistic communication ... as its integral characteristic in terms of the mutual influence of communicants in the process of communication” [7].

In historical pragma linguistics, the analysis of directive speech and discourse is developed on the material of speech communication of remote historical periods, which allows a deeper understanding of the current state of the pragmatic system, on the other hand, and to establish the nature of diachronic changes in speech act and discourse (its strategies and tactics), with another.

The unit of this analysis is a speech act, understood as “a certain set of speech operations or speech acts-functions, characterized by purposefulness, awareness, contextualization, dynamism, and the possibility of both independent use in speech interaction and inclusion in another form of activity” [5]. The linguistic form of speech acts is an utterance - a sentence actualized in speech, used to achieve a communicative goal.

The essence of directive speech acts is most fully defined in speech act theories (SAT). This theory emphasizes as the subject of analysis the pragmatic meaning of an utterance as a result of the speaker uttering a sentence in a situation of direct communication with the listener. According to I.M. Kobozeva, SAT is a logical-philosophical doctrine in its initial premises and linguistic in its results about the structure of the elementary unit of speech communication, mainly interpersonal relationships [4]. On SAT, a speech act is considered as a three-level unity, including three types of actions: locutionary, illocutionary and perlocutionary. A locutionary act is an act of speaking, an illocutionary act is an action

performed in the process of uttering a statement. A perlocutionary act is an influence on the addressee through the utterance of a statement.

When analyzing the evolution of pragma linguistic properties of the directive speech act, linguistic material from distant historical periods is available to the researcher only in the form of written texts. An adequate reflection of the state of oral speech communication of the era is contained in those parts of fiction texts that contain character speech presented in the form of dialogue. Following M.M. Bakhtin, we use the concept of dialogism in its broad interpretation [2].

The use of represented speech as material for historical-pragma linguistic research requires clarification of the constituents of speech act. It is believed that "in the case of oral speech acts, the situation of implementation includes, as a rule, at least two participants in communication (the speaker and the addressee), while in the case of written speech acts - one" [3], however, our position on this issue is less categorical. We proceed from the fact that the communication process requires at least two communicators (individuals or a hypothetical addressee, alter ego). The orientation of the speech act towards the addressee is manifested in the stylistic coloring of the text, in the choice of etiquette forms of address, etc. Thus, in the character-character communication line, both communicants appear as completely real persons [12].

In addition, in written speech the leading characteristics of directive speech act are preserved: firstly, speech acts is an action, secondly, it is realized in speech, therefore, when identifying the historical dynamics of the pragmatic characteristics of communication and analyzing the variability of the constituents of speech act, it is fair to assume in diachrony that the written form discourse presented in fiction is a fairly reliable source of information about speech act and the discourse of distant historical periods, allowing us to adequately describe the trends in the dynamics of the communication system as a whole.

The obtained data from the analysis of the directive speech act suggest a discrepancy between the boundaries of the speech act and the sentence-statement. Theoretically, this is justified by the fact that speech act can be either larger or smaller than a statement and can be implemented as part of a sentence or as a sequence of statements. Thus, T. van Dyck recognizes the possibility of one complex sentence to realize several speech acts: "one illocutionary act is always separated from another by a sentence boundary, while an illocutionary act expressed by one sentence can be compound" [3]. D. Wunderlich argues that a complex speech act can consist of several simple speech acts [9].

Complex speech act is defined by V.I. Karaban as a non-minimal unit of speech, which is "a combination of simple speech acts as minimal speech units, united by one of three types of discursive relations and characterized by a certain discursive function" [15], whereby discursive relations we mean the subordination of the perlocutionary goals of the speech act components of a complex speech act, the coordination of their perlocutionary goals or the facilitating relationship between them. The immediate components of a complex speech act are simple speech act functions and the discursive act of connecting them. Complex speech act, in particular, complex directive speech acts, are characterized by a single post-actor speech intention and function in speech as integral speech units.

One of the important problems of the ongoing historical and pragma linguistic analysis of the directive speech act is the choice of classification of speech acts. In linguistics, several typologies of speech acts are known J. Austin is based on the classification of illocutionary

verbs [1], J. Searle on 12 distinctive features, such as illocutionary verbs, communicative intention, the place of a speech act in discourse, etc. [7], however, in modern linguistics there is no consensus on this issue. In general, J. Versuren divides all known typologies into two large groups: generalizing classifications that distinguish the largest classes of speech act and crushing speech act and their types into smaller units (lumper attitude/splitter attitude) [16]. The objectives of this study are most consistent with an approach focused on identifying the main types of speech act: historical pragma linguistics at the present stage is based on generalized approaches to the classification of speech act, since “for now we can talk about the restoration of pragmatic categories of speech of early historical periods with a large degree of convention, only in the form of general trends, not absolute data” [11].

Thus, in J. Austin’s classification, directives and requests are included in the class of executives [1] along with other speech acts that express the speaker’s use of his power, the exercise of rights, and the exercise of influence.

The directive speech acts as an inducement to action is classified by J. Searle in the same class of speech act together with the request for information - the inducement to speak. J. Searle's speech act system includes the following five types of speech act, identified on the basis of the criterion of the illocutionary goal: directives (inducements to non-verbal action and incentives to a verbal response - asking), assertive, commissive, declarative, expressive.

Etymologically, the English will goes back to the Gothic *wiljan*, *wiliau*, *wileis*. In Germanic languages “want” is recognized as a state associated with “selecting” an object from a certain set, as a state of choice, which determines additional or “passive” signs of the concept “will-wanting”, which are preserved as secondary meanings in modern English will. The dictionary entry for this verb contains the following meanings relevant to our analysis: *wille*, *infin. wyllan*, used to express desire, wish (previously XII century), and in modern language: desire, choice, willingness, consent/refusal, as well as to order or direct by a will, to determine by an act of choice (bequeath, decree, order, intend, purpose, choose). The semantic meanings of the concept “will-wanting” are reflected in speech act verbs corresponding to the directive speech act. The connection of this concept with the desired mood - the optative - is manifested in the fact that this mood is expressed by modal verbs.

The way to categorize speech acts are performative (also called speech act, illocutionary) verbs. From the many different linguistic interpretations of the essence and number of speech act verbs, in this work, following J. Austin [149], we use the concept of a performative verb and highlight its main properties, such as its purpose for indicating the illocutionary force of speech act, the presence of a certain *sem* (*dictum*), the presence of hidden assumptions, assumptions, emotions. Although J. Searle warns that the role of these verbs in establishing the type of speech act should not be exaggerated [6], according to A. Wierzbicka’s definition, the set of speech act verbs of the English language “reflects a certain interpretation of the world of human actions and interactions” [17], which determines social - the cultural specificity of these verbs suggests their diachronic variation.

To distinguish the directive speech act from other speech act types, we will use the criterion of the final intention of the utterance, its temporal reference, the criterion of the subject of the intended action in the utterance, the criterion of the beneficence of the incentive for the addresser and the addressee:

- the final intention of an utterance can be the commission of both non-verbal and verbal actions. And although the speech act quests and directives have a common component of meaning - an incentive, in the first case the utterance implements an incentive, directives, and in the second the illocutionary act of asking is a quesitive;
- the structure of conceptual time in directive speech acts is a combination of the principles of dynamics and statics - indications of the desired action in the future (dynamics) and the correlation of the moment of pronouncing the speech act by the addresser with the present, in accordance with the definition of directive (statics). The correlation of the addresser's plan with the past or future tense of the indicative signals that the utterance implements a constative, expressive or other types of speech act;
- the presence of the subject of the desired action p in the proposition of the utterance allows us to distinguish directives from commissive and their varieties: in directives the action is intended to the listener or a third party, while in commissive the subject of the action is the addressee himself;
- the conceptual distinctive features of the directive speech act from other types of speech act, which include a motivation component in the proposition and convey the concept of "will-wanting", lie in the features of the illocutionary force, in the nature of the intended action and the attitude of the communicants towards it.

The main results of the study described in this chapter are reflected in the author's subsequent publications.

The methodological basis for the undertaken pragma linguistic analysis of speech act in terms of diachrony is the system-activity approach to speech communication, based on the theory of speech activity. Its use allows us to consider aspects of the directive speech act as a system oriented relative to the axes of synchrony and diachrony. Pragmatic phenomena that are stable on the axis of diachrony are recognized as pragmatic constants; phenomena belonging to one of the axes of synchrony within selected time boundaries are pragmatic variables. The unity and contradiction of constants and variables ensures the pragmatic evolution of speech communication - a process of historical variation in aspects of speech act and discourse, based on the principle of asymmetry of interaction between the system and the environment.

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